

THE INFLUENCE OF INADEQUATE COMPUTER SKILLS ON E-LEARNING IN HIGH SCHOOLS

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Abstract: One of the most important factors that contribute to the development and spread of e-learning is the complete efficiency in the use of computers for both students and teachers. It is important and necessary to raise the efficiency of students and teachers during intensive training and short training courses that have an effective and rapid impact. One of the most important factors that limit the development and spread of e-learning is the lack of efficiency in computer use. Education was traditionally in Saudi Arabia, in addition to teaching methods, in recent years, the e-learning approach has been officially adopted by the majority of Saudi schools. The current study aims to achieve the goals of finding the relationship between computer literacy and e-learning situations and exploring the effectiveness and efficiency of educational resources for information technology available in the education system. Building a form to develop computer skills during the intensification of educational courses. Evaluating the model in order to agree that the required solution has been achieved. The researcher used a questionnaire for both students and teachers of both sexes. The typical transformation occurs in teachers when using technology as a new way of teaching and learning. Merging technology into training, teachers must have a positive position as a tool that improves their education and learns the student. Students have seen a generally positive attitude toward teaching and learning technology. They are ready to accept the opportunity in education and request a teacher's participation in excelling in their learning technology.

Keywords: E-learning, Teacher's Efficiency Student.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are many countries from the developed world, each of which has many leading experiences in the field of implementing the various systems of e-learning that started using helpful methods to clarify some concepts and experiences and ended with the application of advanced systems for e-learning and distance education. One of the most important advantages of civilized society. Before adopting information and communications technology in Saudi Arabia, education was conducted according to traditional teaching assets. In recent years, additional efforts have been undertaken to indulge information and communication technology methods in the educational process, as the e-learning approach (e-learning) has been officially adopted by most Saudi schools [1].

E-learning helps and contributes greatly to converting the educational process from a routine process to a more creative, interactive, and developed educational process, where a person who practices e-learning can reach educational materials and choose the time that suits him and this place is suitable for, and in the following, traditional classrooms have become

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unimportant. The education process is implemented in a rich environment with many sources and methods of multiple information [2, 3].

Explains that the IT and Communications technology elements used in a variety of electronic services tools and services are generally divided into four categories: sound tools (video conference, short wave radio, two-way interactive phone, audio, and radio), data (including Data (including electronic service applications, such as computer management training, computer assistance education, through personal computers, including email, telegraph, computer conference, global web), photo tools (slides, movies, videos, Video conferences), and printed media [4].

The main goal of e-learning systems is effective communication between the teacher and the student when interaction face-to-face between the student and the teacher is not possible [5]. The supportive and wireless communication system for electronic services is an important specification for the type of lesson or the quality of the student and the teacher. The appropriate system components should not only be suitable in school but should also be supported at the end of the student in the far place, in order for e-learning to be properly. The development of major information and communications technology that affects the quality of electronic services is the interactive ability; This provides the required comments between the learner and the teacher, as well as the opportunity to exchange ideas and dialogue, clarify messages, and evaluate each other [6, 7].

E-learning services include dividing the subject of the study into educational topics that reflect the school approach to this degree. In the electronic educational services that focus on the team, the teacher shares the teams and individuals through various channels via the Internet such as discussion forums, group email, virtual educational programs or chat rooms, and secret email. In most e-learning programs in Saudi schools, students attend live sessions with trainers. Its sessions feature-rich features (such as video and direct sound), online presentations, and group discussions. One of the other important factors that must be mentioned in this regard is the efficiency and skills of students in the use of the computer and their applications. The efficiency of the e-learning process depends on the ability of teachers and students to use computers and e-learning applications [8, 9].

Despite the widespread development of electronic services provided by Saudi schools and the application of quality standards, the success of the system is related to the ability of teachers and students to deal with e-learning platforms. Accordingly, the proposed study aims to investigate the impact of the lack of computational efficiency for students and teachers in the e-learning process [10].

II. CONTRIBUTION

This study contributes to supporting and encouraging decision makers in the educational system in general in Saudi Arabia to explore the factors that affect the progress and development of electronic education, especially the factor of lack of computer competency for teachers and students and overcoming them, which contributes to building educational and infrastructure platforms that contribute to the spread of electronic education and its acceptance before Teachers and students effectively and attractive.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

Teachers, as well as students, must possess computer use skills and its various devices, as well as software applications in the education and learning process, which leads to reducing the percentage of computer illiteracy of teachers and learners, and thus the prosperity, development, and spread of e-learning effectively and easily, and this, in turn, contributes to improving the education outcomes in a flexible and competency manner. Lack of competency for students and teachers has an effect on the electronic educational process.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A large and selected collection of search philosophies and research methods and their methods was discussed, then the method of collecting data and the method of taking and selecting samples, then designing the questionnaires for those and methods of analyzing these data.

As for the proposed study, counting the quantitative approach is the most appropriate and appropriate to achieve the goals of the study and helps in comparing and collecting data statistically. Investigative studies have been organized on a group

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of teachers and students to assess the effect of computer lack of competency for students and teachers on the process of e-learning and the extent of this on the electronic educational process. Secondary data has been obtained from previous research and literature, such as published magazines, online articles, press articles, and reading materials about the effect of deficiency in the use of computer technology for students and teachers in the electronic educational process. Initial data was used as a guide to how to conduct a study.

V. SAMPLING AND ANALYSIS

Regarding this research, a questionnaire was used as a data collection method. Two questionnaires were published containing nearly 70 questions related to the lack of competency of students and teachers in e-learning, teacher questionnaires were divided into four main domains as follows:

1. E-learning culture.
2. Dealing with internet networks.
3. Educational platforms and learning media design.
4. Computer driving skills.
5. Computer competency's impact on the e-learning process.

And students' questionnaires were divided into four main domains as follows:

1. E-learning culture.
2. The competency to deal with educational platforms.
3. Impact of computer competency on the e-learning process.

These main domains have been broken down into sub-parts to make it easier for participants to attempt the survey. The researcher also used direct interviews, as the interview provides deep and distinctive information to the researcher that is not provided by other study tools, so the researcher dealt with the study sample directly and reached direct answers, as well as monitoring the reaction of the sample through observation and investigate for the factor of lack of computer competency of teachers and student that led to a negative impact on the spread and development of e-learning.

VI. RESULTS

Through the study and analysis of the results of the questionnaire, the data and according to the opinions of the participants indicate the following information: The male teachers were, representing a percentage of 53.6%, while the female teachers were, representing a percentage of 46.4%. The students of girls have represented a percentage of 51.6%, while the students of boys represented a percentage of 48.4%. The descriptive measurements of items show the first domain "E-learning culture", the total degree High with ($M = 4.09$ out of 5, $RII = 81.8\%$, $SD = 0.6$). The total degree of the second domain "Dealing with internet networks" was High with ($M = 4.04$ out of 5, $RII = 80.8\%$, $SD = 0.67$). The total degree of the third domain "Educational platforms and learning media design" was high with ($M = 3.81$ out of 5, $RII = 76.2\%$, $SD = 0.96$). This result indicates a high degree of approval. The total degree of the fourth domain "Computer driving skills" was High with ($M = 3.9$ out of 5, $RII = 78\%$, $SD = 0.85$). This result indicates a high degree of approval. The total degree of the fifth domain "Computer competency's impact on e-learning process" was very high with ($M = 4.41$ out of 5, $RII = 88.2\%$, $SD = 0.63$) This result indicates a very high degree of approval amongst the respondents. The researcher attributes this result to the spread of digital awareness in Saudi society, especially those working in the educational sector, where many teachers and students seek to achieve a deeper understanding of e-learning to enable them to apply it in their work.

VII. CONCLUSION

The Schools in Medina is one that is still developing concerning incorporating technology in the classroom. Teachers and students have been found to have similar attitudes regarding teaching and learning technology. A primary similarity between educators' and learners' attitudes toward training and learning technology is their capacity to associate with it. They also accept technology depending on their prior experience. However, the research paper has established that a paradigm shift occurs in teachers when using technology as a new method of teaching and learning. It is an attitude that teachers have

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because they are not digital natives and have to learn ways of effectively teaching and learning technology. Incorporating technology in training, teachers must have a positive attitude that is a tool that improves their teaching and learning for the student. Students were seen to have an overall positive attitude toward teaching and learning technology. They have a willingness of accepting the change in education and requiring educators' participation in excelling in their learning technology.

Several studies have claimed that the adoption and use of information and communications technology in the educational environment can help and improve the spread of e-learning. However, there are only a few teachers and students who chose to use or employ them as one aspect of their educational practices. As a result, knowing the factors that affect the improvement and development of e-learning through reviewing and highlighting the main worker as the lack of computer competency for students and teachers, which affects the adoption and implementation of information and communications technology in education for learning by teachers and students is very important. After reviewing and providing previous studies, it is clear that lack of competency and lack of training affects the process of adopting and using information and communications technology in the educational process. If these elements are left without a solution, it is likely that it is possible that students' and teachers' dependence on information technology in e-learning will be limited. Consequently, Saudi institutions must develop and develop perfect plans and strategies in order to address these factors. Therefore, the researchers concluded the following points:

- The researcher designed a model that uses some important and effective tools that help students and teachers to improve the level of their computer competency, and all of this leads to optimal use of the electronic educational process.
- The research objectives-in brief - were to present a new idea, which proved its success and effectiveness in improving the computer competency for students and teachers through applying the model of this idea in a tangible practical way, which is short and intensive courses because of its very quick and effective results.
- The idea of short and intensive courses is characterized by not taking a long time, or consuming a lot of money or a lot of effort.
- Many previous studies were discussed by the researcher on computer efficiency in e-learning for students or teachers, both separately and briefly.
- The researcher focused here a closer lens on the source of the problem, and suggested its solution in innovative ways characterized by the d impact, low cost, short time, and, easy application.
- There are many factors that affect the progress, improvement, and spread e-learning process, which needs more research, study, detection, and development of appropriate solutions for these issues.

Based on the study results and discussion, the researcher recommends the following:

Supporting academic plans and curricula in Saudi schools with the practical aspects of information technology and e-learning, to raise the level of pre-service teacher qualification in this field.

Intensifying training courses for teachers in order to develop their competencies in e-learning, preferably electronic programs.

Addressing obstacles to the application of e-learning in Saudi schools by providing laboratories and equipment for this.

Providing the necessary practical training for students in order to raise their abilities in dealing with electronic devices and hardware needed for e-learning.

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